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'Next, next, accept, run'

The difficulties of university software licences

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ABSTRACT

Giving free access (student licenses) to particular software packages is one of the greatest financial support one in their years of education can get from the university or software providers. However, it is worth taking a look at the circumstances of the installation process.

Students at Budapest University of Technology and Economics experienced some serious difficulties while installing MatLab, a multi-paradigm numerical computing environment, which is continuously used during the B.Sc. and M.Sc. studies.

This problem may cause some legal trouble because we all know the similarities between university students and electricity - they follow the path with the lower resistance. University governances should also definitely consider this when setting up their software license-system, as a sufficient number of students will choose illegal ways to get access to a software if it is easier than getting it through the university licence.

We examined mechatronics engineer freshmen (Department for Mechanical Engineering) of the university installing student-licensed MatLab on their own laptops performing (second level) TAP. An open source software, Inkscape was used during the experiment as a reference.

Our main aspects were: how time-consuming and how mentally stressful it is for students to acquire the software.

To get exact and numeric values of the latter, NASA Task Load Index papers were used after each software got installed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Usability testing evaluates ease of use [1], where real end users are testing hardware or software products whilst the process is being monitored by researchers. It does not perfectly mimic real-life use, but it is the closest one can get, and gives relevant results. This type of testing is best with five participants [2] as this way relatively few resources are needed whilst around 85% of the possible problems and stumbling blocks can be

found. Usability testing is also not relatively new practise, earliest sources specifically about usability testing found during our research date back to 1993 [3].

In our research, we focused mainly on the installation progress of software. These days – when one has become so accustomed to software updates and new installs – it has almost become an automatic process one barely pays any attention to, unless facing difficulties, or when having to follow a specific, sometimes counter-intuitive process.

Such specific processes often make an appearance in the installation of software for student use. This article will be focusing on software packages intended for use by engineering B.Sc. and M.Sc. students, more specifically how these software packages can be claimed and installed.

Starting an engineering B.Sc. can be overwhelming considering all the new impressions, one of which is all the new software that is to be installed and put to use. The software can be divided into several sub-categories[4] such as freeware, single user licences which are linked to site registration, software distributed by the university, multi-user licences etc.

When starting university, students of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem, BME) do not get onboarded in a sense that they get a full software package or complete instructions on how to obtain all required software for the respectable faculty, instead there is sporadic information given by the university along with some student-to-student guides. There are many possibilities for legal downloads for software like MS Windows and Office, Ansys, Wolfram Mathematica, Autodesk Inventor, Catia, Creo, SolidWorks, MatLab etc., which all have very different processes for acquiring the licences.

In this paper the aim is to bring forward the process of the MatLab installation, and to point out the many stumbling blocks that can pop up during the process. There is a site operated by the IT directorate of the university, which was specially created to describe and help with the process of the MatLab installation, however multiple ways are listed on how the software can be installed legally, none of which is clear-cut.

For this research we performed a usability test on the MatLab installation progress. Participants were asked to think aloud while performing the installation, while it was emphasized, that it is not their performance that is measured, but rather the reoccurring problems in the installation process.

2 METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study was to measure the following characteristics of the installation process of MatLab with student licence at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics:

- installation time;
- frequently occurring errors;
- and the strain the process puts on students.

The study took place at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, building Q. Six participants were included, who studied mechatronics and were in the

beginning of their second semester of B.Sc. the time the study was performed. We analysed the study's sixth participant's case later; the whole task was completed by five people. All but one of the participants were male, with relatively high experience in the field of informatics.

We informed the participants about the purpose and details of the study and assured about the safety of their personal data and that not their performance, but the installation process is being investigated. We also informed them about the scientific method, which was used: level 2 Thinking Aloud Protocol.[5]

The circumstances of the study were equal in all six cases: the same room and wired Internet connection was used. (MatLab can only be installed using the university network or VPN). Minimum two of us were present to obtain objective results.

To complete the installation process with this kind of licence, one must possess a registration to a university server. Since this registration process has an estimated lead-time of two to three hours, we asked the participants in an e-mail to complete this registration in advance. This preparation did not affect the testing of the installation procedure.

The participants used their own laptops for installation purposes, we compensated the variances in download and installation time, that arose from the performance-differences of the computers during the analyzation.

We used a questionnaire in order to collect information about the awareness about student licences provided by the University. We wanted to find out whether participants have known about the following free student software before the study application: Windows10, Office365, MatLab.

Since none of the participants were familiar with the TAP method before the study, we added a training exercise to the research. We asked the study subjects to think aloud while downloading and installing a free screen and voice recording software, ThunderSoft Screen Recorder[6], the recordings of which were the main source of information and data (time, recorded video of the screen and the voice of the participant) for the analyzation. We used another voice recording device (a mobile phone) as data authentication.

This training task was not recorded. The recorded and examined study contained the download and installation of two software packages: Inkscape [7], an open source drawing software (used as a sample to estimate the temper and attitude towards software installing of participants) and MatLab, the main subject of the study, a multi-paradigm numerical computing environment developed by MathWorks.

We sent an e-mail to the participants, which included the two webpages, from where the examined processes started. To each exercise belonged two worksheets: one for the subject, which included the detailed steps of the exercise and one for us on which the common mistakes (guideline was created pre-research based on our personal experiences), successfulness of the participants and notes were marked.

After each exercise we asked the subjects to fill in a Nasa Task Load Index paper [8] (translated to Hungarian by us), which measured the participants' subjective opinion on the exercise and on their own performance.

Finishing both tasks, we asked participants to grade the study itself and the our attitude. We also graded the subjects according to the following aspects: experience with computers, tiredness after the tasks, attitude to the tasks, attitude to (incidental) failures, efficiency of the TAP method-usage.

We fed the collected data into a spreadsheet software, which was used for analyzation as well. The analysation was led through the frequently occurring mistakes of participants (rated with checkboxes) and successfulness of the participants (rated on bars 1-5; 1 – could not absolve the task; 5 – perfectly completed without help).

The whole recorded time/participant was divided into: Inkscape time, MatLab time and NASA TLX time, which was not counted as valuable working time. Both the MatLab and Inkscape times can be divided into 'thinking' and 'loading' time. Since the 'loading' time depends on the computer, the study concentrated on comparing the pure 'thinking' times of the two software packages. We also examined the correlation between the experience with computers (the researchers' subjective opinion on participants) and time (participants spent on finding the way of installation).

The evaluation of NASA Task Load Index papers was essentially the visualization of rating scales.

3 RESULTS

The data collection resulted in 6 hours, 26 minutes and 55 seconds of screen videos and voice records. The notes made of analysing these data take up six A4 pages.

Since the participants used their own laptops for the study, it was important to eliminate the ascending differences. The solution for this problem is to compare the previously defined 'thinking' times instead of all the times needed for each software.

An important part was to evaluate the results of the NASA Task Load Index paper, since one of the study's most important aims was to examine the strain the process

puts on students. The results show, how participants felt about the installation process of each software.

It was also interesting, which of the pre-determined mistakes in the installation process, based on our personal experiences occurred most frequently.

Mistake	Frequency
Gets lost in the guide on the website of the BME IT directorate	4
Can not log into the @hszk.bme.hu e-mail account	4
Gets distracted by the 'set location' pop up window on the website of Mathworks	3
Gets confused about the licence assignment	3
Gets confused about the warning sign showing the end of the licence period on the website of the BME IT directorate	2
Does not tick 'I agree' when signing in to the BME accadmin account	2
Does not find his e-mail address on the BME accadmin interface	2
Does not know his password to his @hszk.bme.hu e-mail account	2

Table 1. Pre-determined mistakes in the installation process

Fig. 2. NASA Taskload Index: average values of participants' answers

No other mistake with the frequency of more than one occurred during the study.

The main steps of the installation process were rated on a bar.

0	1	2	3
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where:

0 means the participant could not complete the process

1 means the participant could do the task, but with a lot of help

2 means the participant could do the task, but needed a little help

3 means the participant could do the task without any help

Task	Average score
Finds 'ways of installing MatLab for students'	2.6
Logs in to his accadmin account	2.2
Creates Mathworks user account	1.6
Verifies his Mathworks account	3.2
Downloads the installer from his Mathworks account	2.8
Logs in to his Mathworks account inside the installer	3

Table 2. Average scores of task bar gradings

In one case, rating the e-mail verification process (containing logging into the hszk e-mail account), we used a longer bar (with 5 options for rating).

This chart shows that no real correlation between the subjective value we assigned to each participant from the aspect of experience in the field of informatics and the 'thinking' time of each software.

4 DISCUSSION

We concluded this study because we had found it extremely difficult to install this software on our computers and wanted to help the next generation of students by identifying the main problems of the installation process and making suggestions to improve it. The above discussed problems encountered by the participants which occurred during the installation process could be derived from some well outlined sources, mainly associated with the IT infrastructure of the university.

First, the students had to receive information about the existence of the university's MatLab student license. It would be considered trivial, whilst this information is mainly spread verbally and by some posters around the building of the Institute of Mathematics.

After making the decision to install the software on their computer an overcomplicated guide about every possible way of the installation process is provided on the site of the BME IT directorate. The guide lacks the description of some non-trivial steps of the installation and lead the participants to a set of not quite ergonomic webpages. Furthermore, the guide is only available on the university's local network (or via VPN), which is quite inauspicious taking the usual 90-120 minutes length of the installation process into consideration.

During the installation process the students have to use several accounts and login credentials associated with different departments of the university. This caused serious drawbacks for the participants, who confused these accounts and could not find out what their passwords were since none of them used a password-manager. Some steps of the process, particularly requesting access to the mail server and changing the password associated with the webmail service require up to 2 hours (added to the usual 90-minute installation length), or even more on weekends. This is enough time to make the students rethink their decision about the installation or just simply forget about starting it at all.

Finally, after all these hurdles the otherwise ergonomic website of MathWorks made it quite difficult for the participants to find the download icon for the installer. We even had a sixth participant who completed the whole licence acquisition process and only applied for the research to get help finding this icon.

After downloading the installer the installation ran smoothly until the point where they could choose between two ways to associate the university student license with the installed software: by logging in to the software with their account or by typing in a licence key that is provided on the website of the BME IT directorate. The first method is totally sufficient and the presence of the second one in the installation guide only made the participants hesitate.

These difficulties could possibly lead university students to illegal solutions, causing financial disadvantage for the university, the software developer and their own legal endangerment.

Whilst organizing the results and clarifying the suggested installation process an exploit was found. The BME Matlab licence works by associating a licence based on the email address of the registered MathWorks account. Therefore, everyone in

possession of an email address ending with 'bme.hu' is eligible for a BME Matlab licence. However, students have two of these email addresses the one from the Student Computer Centre (Hallgatói Számítógép Központ, HSZK, @hszk.bme.hu) and the one for the BME Microsoft Office Student licence (the @edu.bme.hu). Acquiring an additional Matlab licence for the same student but with the @edu.bme.hu email address was successful implying that every student of BME could have at least two.

For the future, we suggest the simplification of the credentials associated with the students by giving students one university email address (@edu.bme.hu), which could be used to manage every and any IT system connected to their studies. We also imply the creation of the matlab.bme.hu website with a simplified, univocal guide for students on the frontpage about the installation process that is accessible not just on the university network. We would like to cast light on the problem of multiple licences. For now, we suggest the use of the @edu.bme.hu email address for students to acquire the licence simply and without having to use outdated, not ergonomic, confusing websites.

This research could be used to provide methodology for other software installation usability tests. We fulfilled our main goals with the research by confirming that the current method of installation is not optimal, by determining the main obstacles and by finding a more straight-forward way for the installation. Our suggestions will be sent to the responsible personnel at the Institute of Mathematics, and hopes are that by cooperation, the installation process can be reviewed by the start of summer 2019.

5 CONCLUSION

As a summary, we performed the planned TAP interviews, recorded and analysed data. We found no correlation between the subjective experience of the participants in IT and the 'thinking' time of each software. The 'thinking' time for MatLab was on average 10 times longer than that of Inkscape and the participants subjectively found it to be more difficult. We found that the information about the licence and the installation process is mainly spread by student-to-student communication rather than via emails and websites from an official source. We discovered missing steps in the installation guide that could be considered the main reason for the long installation. The several accounts and credentials the participants had to use during the installation confused them. The problem of multiple licences for students was revealed during the end phase of the research. The not suggested second acquisition process took less steps, time and was similar to an ordinary student licence activation, like Autodesk's.

For the future, we suggest the simplification of the credentials by managing every and any IT system connected to the university with one email address. We propose the creation of matlab.bme.hu to provide an optimal guide for the installation. For now, we imply the use of the @edu.bme.hu email address for the acquisition of the university's MatLab licence.

The research could be continued by designing the matlab.bme.hu website and measuring the number of its visitors and the number of MatLab licence activations.

Despite all the problems this study discussed about the installation process of MatLab, the availability of this software is a great support from the university for students. With

just a few changes introduced in the installation process, the rate of students using the university's MatLab license legally could see a substantial increase. We hope to see these changes in the future and that our study provides help for all the involved personnel.

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